

Discovery of a recessive tall somatic mutant with wide compatibility in *Oryza sativa* L.

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A recessive tall somatic mutant with wide compatibility, 02428h, was created by somatic culture of mature embryos from japonica 02428. Elongated upper first and second internodes caused the tallness. The R_1 and R_2 height segregation, derived from the R_2 semidwarf plant line, fit a 3

Plant classification of progenies of long-culm mutant 02428h, 1990.

Generation	Total plants (no.)	Normal semidwarf type (no.)	Tall type (no.)	Semidwarf: tall	Probability
R_2	40	29	11	0.033	0.75-0.90
R_3	85	63	22	0.004	0.95-0.99
R_4	44	32	12	0.03	0.75-0.90
F_2	651	489	162	0.0005	0.95-0.99

semidwarf:1 tall ratio. The F_1 height of the cross 02428h and semidwarf 02428 in 1990 was the same as that of 02428 (88 cm). The F_2 height also fit the 3 semidwarf:1 tall ratio (see table). The results indicate that a single recessive gene controls the long culm mutation.

02428h was also crossed in 1990 with

indica varieties IR36, Nanjing 11, and 3037. The F_1 plants of all three had high fertility, with an average of 81.34%, indicating that the mutant 02428h maintained the wide compatibility of 02428. 02428h will be very useful in rice interspecific and intersubspecific hybrid seed production. ■

Performance of experimental rice hybrids in Bangalore, Karnataka, India

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We evaluated 11 hybrids of varying durations against local checks Jaya, Rasi, IR20, and Mangala at the Main Rice

Research Station, Hebbal, Bangalore, during the 1991 wet season. We transplanted 30-d-old seedlings at 15- × 15-cm spacing on 7 Aug 1991 in 7.9-m² plots laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

IR58025 A combinations generally outperformed IR62829 A and V20 A hybrids. ORI 002, IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R, and ORI 001 yielded higher than others (see table). Estimates

in relation to checks of comparable duration revealed standard heterosis of 38.5% for ORI 002 (130 d), 41.0% for IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R (128 d), 20.0% for IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R (117 d), and 36.3% for IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R (124 d).

The same hybrids have performed well with standard heterosis of 7.1-35.4% at Mandya, Karnataka, and are being grown in farmers' fields for verification. ■

Performance of experimental hybrids at Bangalore, Karnataka, India, 1991 wet season.

Hybrid, check	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%) over			
							Jaya	Rasi	IR20	Mangala
Hybrid										
V20 A/IR30864	116	69	315	146	48.6	3.2	-61.9	-27.2	-43.8	-36.0
IR62829 A/IET11691	110	99	470	146	74.4	3.8	-54.7	-13.6	-33.3	-24.0
IR62829 A/IR30864	130	82	400	157	71.1	3.0	-64.2	-31.8	-47.3	-40.0
V20 A/IRBB7	120	57	398	92	21.1	4.7	-44.0	6.8	-17.5	-6.0
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3 R	124	76	459	168	45.2	6.0	-28.5	36.3	5.2	20.0
IR58025 A/IRBB4	138	79	418	202	32.3	5.9	-29.7	34.0	3.5	18.0
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	117	77	420	154	41.0	6.0	-28.5	36.3	5.2	20.0
IR58025 A/IR35366-62-1-2-2-3 R	128	81	494	116	53.2	6.2	-26.1	41.0	8.7	24.0
ORI 001	137	81	430	172	47.7	6.2	-26.1	41.0	8.7	24.0
ORI 002	130	83	401	168	27.1	7.9	-5.9	79.5	38.5	58.0
ORI 005	140	78	405	191	50.7	4.1	-51.1	-6.8	-28.0	-18.0
Check										
Jaya	140	92	384	147	24.2	8.4				
Rasi	126	88	392	162	7.6	4.4				
IR20	138	83	576	167	26.9	5.7				
Mangala	118	72	416	73	14.2	5.0				
LSD						0.4				
CV (%)						9.8				